

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. DOMAIN INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning

Machine learning is an application of artificial intelligence (AI) that provides systems the ability to automatically learn and improve from experience without being explicitly programmed. Machine learning focuses on the development of computer programs that can access data and use it learn for themselves. The process of learning begins with observations or data, such as examples, direct experience, or instruction, in order to look for patterns in data and make better decisions in the future based on the examples that we provide. The primary aim is to allow the computers learn automatically without human intervention or assistance and adjust actions accordingly.

Machine Learning Methods

Machine learning algorithms are often categorized as supervised or unsupervised. **Supervised machine learning algorithms** can apply what has been learned in the past to new data using labeled examples to predict future events. Starting from the analysis of a known training dataset, the learning algorithm produces an inferred function to make predictions about the output values. The system is able to provide targets for any new input after sufficient training. The learning algorithm can also compare its output with the correct, intended output and find errors in order to modify the model accordingly.

In contrast, **unsupervised machine learning algorithms** are used when the information used to train is neither classified nor labeled. Unsupervised learning studies how systems can infer a function to describe a hidden structure from unlabeled data. The system doesn't figure out the right output, but it explores the data and can draw inferences from datasets to describe hidden structures from unlabeled data.

Semi-supervised machine learning algorithms fall somewhere in between supervised and unsupervised learning, since they use both labeled and unlabeled data for training – typically a small amount of labeled data and a large amount of unlabeled data. The systems that use this method are able to considerably improve learning accuracy. Usually, semi-supervised learning is chosen when the acquired labeled data requires skilled and relevant resources in order to train it / learn from it. Otherwise, acquiring unlabeled data generally doesn't require additional resources.

Reinforcement machine learning algorithms is a learning method that interacts with its environment by producing actions and discovers errors or rewards. Trial and error search and delayed reward are the most relevant characteristics of reinforcement learning. This method allows machines and software agents to automatically determine the ideal behavior within a specific context in order to maximize its performance. Simple reward feedback is required for the agent to learn which action is best; this is known as the reinforcement signal.

Advantages of Machine Learning

Machine Learning undoubtedly helps people to work more creatively and efficiently. Basically, you too can delegate quite complex or monotonous work to the computer through Machine Learning - starting with scanning, saving and filing paper documents such as invoices up to organizing and editing images.

In addition to these rather simple tasks, self-learning machines can also perform complex tasks. These include, for example, the recognition of error patterns. This is a major advantage, especially in areas such as the manufacturing industry: the industry relies on continuous and error-free production. While even experts often cannot be sure where and by which correlation a production error in a plant fleet arises, Machine Learning offers the possibility to identify the error early this saves down times and money. Self-learning programs are now also used in the medical field. In the future, after "consuming" huge amounts of data (medical publications, studies, etc.), apps will be able to warn a in case his doctor wants to prescribe a drug that he cannot tolerate. This "knowledge" also means that the app can propose alternative options which for example also take into account the genetic requirements of the respective patient.

1.2. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

A facial recognition system is a computer application for automatically identifying or verifying a person from a digital image or a video frame from a video source. Proposed paper uses face recognition technique for verification in ATM system. For face recognition, there are two types of comparisons. The first is Verification this is where the system compares the given individual with who that individual says they are and gives a yes or no decision. The next one is identification this is where the system compares the given individual to all the other individuals in the database and gives a ranked list of matches. Face recognition technology analyzes the unique shape, pattern and positioning of the facial features. Face recognition is very complex technology and is largely software based. This Biometric Methodology establishes the analysis framework with PCA algorithms for each type of biometric device. Face recognition starts with a picture, attempting to find a person in the image. This can be accomplished using several methods including face, skin tones.

1.3 PROBLEM DEFINITION:

The first challenge was to correctly detect the hand with a webcam. We needed a Computer Vision library for this purpose. Many are available but we decided to go ahead with OpenCV as it is the most popular and has been ported to many languages and is supported on many operating systems from Android to Windows. It has a good library collection of standard image processing functions. Then we had to first setup OpenCV on our IDE(ANACONDA NAVIGATOR). That was a very tedious task. We also had to learn some basic usage of OpenCV. For which we referred to many tutorials on the web. After learning OpenCV, We had to learn about the skin

detection techniques and image processing techniques like Background Subtraction, Image Smoothing, Noise Removal and Reduction.

Now, after face from camera, we had to learn to use the Windows API in order tune the software with the Metro UI. For learning it, we built some basic applications based on it. So, in short, there was a steep learning curve.

As, high-end cameras and sensors are very costly we decided to go with a simple webcam. So, we decided to optimize our software and its functionality in order the drawback of using a simple webcam. Also, for testing our project we had a primary requirement of having a proper web camera with no visible part except our plam.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE SURVEY

PAPER 1: “Deep hypersphere embedding for face recognition”

AUTHOR: W.Liu ,Y.Wen ,Z.Yu, M.Li,B.Raj and L.Song

YEAR: 2017

DESCRIPTION:

This paper addresses deep face recognition (FR) problem under open-set protocol, where ideal face features are expected to have smaller maximal intra-class distance than minimal inter-class distance under a suitably chosen metric space. However, few existing algorithms can effectively achieve this criterion. To this end, we propose the angular softmax (A-Softmax) loss that enables convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to learn angularly discriminative features. Geometrically, A-Softmax loss can be viewed as imposing discriminative constraints on a hypersphere manifold, which intrinsically matches the prior that faces also lie on a manifold. Moreover, the size of angular margin can be quantitatively adjusted by a parameter m . We further derive specific m to approximate the ideal feature criterion. Extensive analysis and experiments on Labeled Face in the Wild (LFW), Youtube Faces (YTF) and MegaFace Challenge 1 show the superiority of A-Softmax loss in FR tasks. SphereFace is a recently proposed face recognition method. It was initially described in paper and then published. The most up-to-date paper with more experiments can be found at arXIV. To facilitate the face recognition research, we give an example of training on CAISIA and testing LFW.

PAPER 2: “Heterogenous Face Recognition using Neural based network”

AUTHORS: Md Rashedul Islam ; UmmeyKulsumMitu ; Rasel Ahmed Bhuiyan ; Jungpil Shin

YEAR: 2018

DESCRIPTION:

Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) is a fascinating field about the interaction between humans and computers. Interacting with computers, human Hand Gesture Recognition (HGR) is the most significant way and the major part of HCI. Extracting features and detecting hand gesture from inputted color videos is more challenging because of the huge variation in the hands. For resolving this issue, this paper introduces an effective HGR system for low-cost color video using webcam. In this proposed model, Deep Convolutional Neural Network (DCNN) is used for extracting efficient hand features to recognize the American Sign Language (ASL) using hand gestures. Finally, the Multi-class Support Vector Machine (MCSVM) is used for identifying the hand sign, where CNN extracted features are used to train up the machine. Distinct person hand gesture is used for validation in this paper. The proposed model shows satisfactory performance in terms of classification accuracy, i.e., 94.57%. Therefore, the primary goal of this research is to obtain a real-time face recognition model for various applications in the field of medicine and engineering with a higher recognition accuracy than the real-time models proposed in the scientific literature and a higher number of gestures to recognize (i.e. in the order of the dozens).

PAPER 3: “Real-time face recognition with EMG using machine learning”

AUTHORS: Andrés G. Jaramillo ; Marco E. Benalcázar, 2017

YEAR: 2017

DESCRIPTION:

In this paper, we propose the development of a model for real-time face recognition. We use surface electromyography (EMG) and Machine Learning techniques. The recognition of face using EMG is not a trivial task because there are several physiological processes in the skeletal muscles underlying their generation. In the scientific literature, there are several face recognition models, but they have limitations both in the number of gestures to be recognized (i.e., classes) and in the processing time. Therefore, the primary goal of this research is to obtain a real-time face recognition model for various applications in the field of medicine and engineering with a higher recognition accuracy than the real-time models proposed in the scientific literature and a higher number of gestures to recognize (i.e. in the order of the dozens). The proposed model has five stages: acquisition of the EMG signals, preprocessing (e.g., rectification and filtering), feature extraction (e.g., time, frequency and time-frequency), classification (e.g., parametric and nonparametric) and post-processing. Generally, the main difficulties of the face recognition models with EMG using Machine Learning are: the noisy behavior of EMG signal, and the small number of gestures per person relative to the number of generated data by each gesture (i.e, curse of dimensionality). Solving these two issues could also lead to solutions for other problems such as face recognition and audio recognition, for which these two issues are a major concern.

PAPER 4: Facial expression recognition from near-infrared video sequences

AUTHOR: G.Zhao,X.Huang,M.Tainin,S.Z.Li and M.Pietikainen

YEAR: 2011

DESCRIPTION:

Facial expressions can be thought as specific dynamic textures where local appearance and motion information need to be taken into account. We utilize local spatiotemporal operators to describe facial expressions. All current facial expression recognition databases are captured in visible light spectrum. Visual light usually changes with locations, and can also vary with time, which can cause significant variations in image appearance and texture. In this paper, we present a novel research on a dynamic facial expression recognition from near-infrared (NIR) video sequences. NIR imaging is robust with respect to illumination changes. Experiments on a new NIR database show promising and robust results against illumination variations. Facial emotion recognition is an emerging field which use in many nowadays application including social robots, neuromarketing and games. Non-verbal communication methods like facial expressions, eye movement and gestures are used in many application of human computer interaction, which among them facial emotion is widely used because it convey the emotional states and feelings of persons. The emotion recognition is not an easy task because there is no landmark distinction between the emotions on the face and also there are a lot of complexity and variability. In the traditional machine learning algorithm some important extracted features used for modelling the face, so, it can not achieve high accuracy rate for recognition of emotion because the features are hand-engineered.

PAPER 5: “The FERET evaluation methodology for face-recognition algorithms”

AUTHOR: P.J.Phillips,H.Moon,S.A.Rizvi,P.JRauss

YEAR: 2000

DESCRIPTION:

Two of the most critical requirements in support of producing reliable face-recognition systems are a large database of facial images and a testing procedure to evaluate systems. The Face Recognition Technology (FERET) program has addressed both issues through the FERET database of facial images and the establishment of the FERET tests. To date, 14,126 images from 1,199 individuals are included in the FERET database, which is divided into development and sequestered portions of the database. In September 1996, the FERET program administered the third in a series of FERET face-recognition tests. The primary objectives of the third test were to 1) assess the state of the art, 2) identify future areas of research, and 3) measure algorithm performance. The Face Recognition Technology (FERET) program database is a large database of facial images, divided into development and sequestered portions. The development portion is made available to researchers, and the sequestered portion is reserved for testing face recognition algorithms. The FERET evaluation procedure is an independently administered test of face-recognition algorithms. The test was designed to: (1) allow a direct comparison between different algorithms, (2) identify the most promising approaches, (3) assess the state of the art in face recognition, (4) identify future directions of research, and (5) advance the state of the art in face recognition.

PAPER 6: “ Learning face representation from scratch”

AUTHOR: Dong Yi, Stan Z Li

YEAR: Nov 2014

Description:

Pushing by big data and deep convolutional neural network (CNN), the performance of face recognition is becoming comparable to human. Using private large scale training datasets, several groups achieve very high performance on LFW, i.e., 97% to 99%. While there are many open source implementations of CNN, none of large scale face dataset is publicly available. The current situation in the field of face recognition is that data is more important than algorithm. To solve this problem, this paper proposes a semi-automatic way to collect face images from Internet and builds a large scale dataset containing about 10,000 subjects and 500,000 images, called CASIAWebFace. Based on the database, we use a 11-layer CNN to learn discriminative representation and obtain state-of-the-art accuracy on LFW and YTF. The publication of CASIAWebFace will attract more research groups entering this field and accelerate the development of face recognition in the wild. While there are many open source implementations of CNN, none of large scale face dataset is publicly available. The current situation in the field of face recognition is that data is more important than algorithm. We explicitly reformulate the layers as learning residual functions with reference to the layer inputs, instead of learning unreferenced functions. We provide comprehensive empirical evidence showing that these residual networks are easier to optimize, and can gain accuracy from considerably increased depth.

PAPER 7: “Deep residual learning for image recognition”

AUTHOR: Kaiming He, Jian Sun

YEAR: Dec 2016

Description:

Deeper neural networks are more difficult to train. We present a residual learning framework to ease the training of networks that are substantially deeper than those used previously. We explicitly reformulate the layers as learning residual functions with reference to the layer inputs, instead of learning unreferenced functions. We provide comprehensive empirical evidence showing that these residual networks are easier to optimize, and can gain accuracy from considerably increased depth. On the ImageNet dataset we evaluate residual nets with a depth of up to 152 layers - 8× deeper than VGG nets [40] but still having lower complexity. An ensemble of these residual nets achieves 3.57% error on the ImageNet test set. This result won the 1st place on the ILSVRC 2015 classification task. We also present analysis on CIFAR-10 with 100 and 1000 layers. The depth of representations is of central importance for many visual recognition tasks. Solely due to our extremely deep representations, we obtain a 28% relative improvement on the COCO object detection dataset. Deep residual nets are foundations of our submissions to ILSVRC & COCO 2015 competitions¹, where we also won the 1st places on the tasks of ImageNet detection, ImageNet localization, COCO detection, and COCO segmentation.

PAPER 8: “Memetically optimized MCWLD for matching sketches with digital face images”

AUTHOR: Mayank Vasta

YEAR: Dec 2015

Description:

One of the important cues in solving crimes and apprehending criminals is matching sketches with digital face images. This paper presents an automated algorithm that extracts discriminating information from local regions of both sketches and digital face images. Structural information along with minute details present in local facial regions are encoded using multiscale circular Weber’s local descriptor. Further, an evolutionary memetic optimization is proposed to assign optimal weights to every local facial region to boost the identification performance. Since, forensic sketches or digital face images can be of poor quality, a pre-processing technique is used to enhance the quality of images and improve the identification performance. Comprehensive experimental evaluation on different sketch databases show that the proposed algorithm yields better identification performance compared to existing face recognition algorithms and two commercial face recognition systems. Especially, our new approach achieves the best results on MegaFace (the largest public domain face benchmark) under the protocol of small training set (contains under 500000 images and under 20000 persons), significantly improving the previous results and setting new state-of-the-art for both face recognition and face verification tasks

PAPER 9: “A discriminative feature learning approach for deep face recognition”

AUTHOR: Yandong Wen

YEAR: Sep 2016

Description:

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have been widely used in computer vision community, significantly improving the state-of-the-art. In most of the available CNNs, the softmax loss function is used as the supervision signal to train the deep model. In order to enhance the discriminative power of the deeply learned features, this paper proposes a new supervision signal, called center loss, for face recognition task. Specifically, the center loss simultaneously learns a center for deep features of each class and penalizes the distances between the deep features and their corresponding class centers. More importantly, we prove that the proposed center loss function is trainable and easy to optimize in the CNNs. With the joint supervision of softmax loss and center loss, we can train a robust CNNs to obtain the deep features with the two key learning objectives, inter-class dispersion and intra-class compactness as much as possible, which are very essential to face recognition. It is encouraging to see that our CNNs(with such joint supervision) achieve the state-of-the-art accuracy on several important face recognition benchmarks, Labeled Faces in the Wild (LFW), YouTube Faces (YTF), and MegaFace Challenge.

PAPER 10:

TITLE: “ Mutual component convolutional neural networks for heterogeneous face recognition”

AUTHOR: Xaijong Peng

YEAR: Jan 2019

Description:

Heterogeneous face recognition (HFR) aims to identify a person from different facial modalities, such as visible and near-infrared images. The main challenges of HFR lie in the large modality discrepancy and insufficient training samples. In this paper, we propose the mutual component convolutional neural network (MC-CNN), a modal-invariant deep learning framework, to tackle these two issues simultaneously. Our MC-CNN incorporates a generative module, i.e., the mutual component analysis (MCA), into modern deep CNNs by viewing MCA as a special fully connected (FC) layer. Based on deep features, this FC layer is designed to extract modal-independent hidden factors and is updated according to maximum likelihood analytic formulation instead of back propagation which prevents overfitting from limited data naturally. In addition, we develop an MCA loss to update the network for modal-invariant feature learning. Extensive experiments show that our MC-CNN outperforms several fine-tuned baseline models significantly. Our methods achieve the state-of-the-art performance on the CASIA NIR-VIS 2.0, CUHK NIR-VIS, and IIIT-D Sketch datasets.

CHAPTER 3

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing ATM system authenticates transactions via the card and PIN based system. Thereafter, it grants access to bank transactions. The ATM system compares the PIN entered against the stored authorization PIN for every ATM user. If there is a match the system authenticates the user and grants access to all services available via ATM. If there is a mismatch the user authentication process fails and the user is given two more opportunities to enter the correct PIN. If the incorrect PIN is entered the card gets blocked and retained by the ATM. Nowadays fingerprint have been implemented in a few ATM system, but it can also lead to fraud. Hackers could use the stolen fingerprint easily to break into the security system.

3.1.1 Drawbacks of Existing System

- ✓ Fraud criminal can fit skimmer device and small cameras to ATM.
- ✓ Not highly secured.
- ✓ Card retention ATMs give but they can also take.
- ✓ No high performance.
- ✓ Theft risk if you go to bank you are likely walking into a secured area watching by multiple cameras or a life guard.

3.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system is an enhancement of the existing system. It will improve the security of the ATM by applying three levels of security for authentication. The proposed system replaces the traditional card and RFID cards used as ATM card, IR sensor in order to sense the presence of the card holders and to turn on fan and light ,If ATM is tampered the SMS is sent to two main stations via GSM.

Based on WI fall detection get security ,that network is not secured that much. The study is focused on Design and Implementation of face detection based ATM security using Embedded Linux platform. The system is implemented on open source computer vision(open CV) software which is used for image processing operation. High level security mechanism is provided by consecutive actions such as initially system captures the human face and check whether human face is detected properly or not .If not detected properly it send the warning message to adjust the position of user. Still the face is not detected properly the system will lock the door of the ATM cabin for security purpose.

Haar Cascade Algorithm

Haar Cascade is a machine learning object detection algorithm used to identify objects in an image or video.

The algorithm has four stages:

1. Haar Feature Selection
2. Creating Integral Images
3. Adaboost Training
4. Cascading Classifiers

3.2.1 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM:

1. Highly secured
2. High performance
3. Withdraw process can be accomplished by either parties.
4. Very less interaction with the ATM machine but with a formal approach.
5. No human intention needed.

3.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

The feasibility of the project is analyzed in this phase and business proposal is put forth with a very general plan for the purpose and some cost estimates. During system analysis the feasibility study of the proposed system is carried out. This ensure that the proposed system is not a burden to the company. For feasibility analysis, some understanding of the major requirements for the system is essential. Consequently benefits are estimated with greater accuracy at this stage. The key considerations are:

- Economic feasibility
- Technical feasibility
- Social feasibility

3.3.1 ECONOMIC FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the economic impact that the system will have on the organization. The amount of fund that the company can pour into the research and development of the system is limited. The expenditures must be justified. Thus the development of the system as well within the budget and this was achieved because most of the technologies used are freely available. Only the customized products had to be purchased.

3.3.2 TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY

This study is carried out to check the feasibility, that is, the technical requirements of the system. Any system developed must not have a high demand on the available technical resources. This will lead to high demands being placed on the client. The developed system must have a modest requirement, as only minimal or null changes are required for implementing this system.

3.3.3 SOCIAL FEASIBILITY

The aspect of study is to check the level of acceptance of the system by the user. This includes the process of training the user to use the system efficiently. The user must not feel threatened by the system, instead must accept it as a necessity. The level of acceptance by the users solely depends on the methods that are employed to educate the user about the system and to make him familiar with it. His level of confidence must be raised so that he is also able to make some constructive criticism, which is welcomed, as he is the final user of the system.

CHAPTER 4

SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1. ARCHITECTURE DIAGRAM

Fig 4.1 Architecture Diagram

4.2. DATA FLOW DIAGRAM

- A data flow diagram (DFD) is a graphical representation of the “flow” of data through an information system, modeling its process aspects. Often, they are a preliminary step used to create an overview of the system which can later be elaborated. DFDs can also be used for the visualization of data processing.

0th Level:

Fig.4.2 Level 0 Dataflow Diagram

1st Level:

Fig 4.3 Level 1 Dataflow Diagram

2nd Level:

Fig 4.3 Level 2 Dataflow Diagram

4.3. UML DIAGRAMS

4.3.1. Use case Diagram

A use case diagram at its simplest is a representation of a user's interaction with the system and depicting the specification of a use case. A use case diagram can portray the different types of users of a system and the various ways that they interact with the system.

4.3.1. Use case Diagram

4.3.2 Sequence Diagram:

A Sequence diagram in Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a kind of interaction diagram that shows how process operate with one another and in what order. It is a construct of a Message Sequence Chart.

Fig 4.6 Sequence Diagram

4.3.3 Activity Diagram

Activity diagrams are graphical representation of workflows of stepwise activities and actions with support for choice, iteration and concurrency. In the Unified Modeling Language, activity diagrams are intended to a model both computational and organizational processes.

Fig 4.7 Activity Diagram

4.3.4 Class Diagram

The class diagram is the main building block of object-oriented modeling. It is used for general conceptual modeling of the structure of the application, and for detailed modeling translating the models into programming code. Class diagrams can also be used for data modeling.

Fig 4.8 Class Diagram

CHAPTER 5

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

5.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

The most common set of requirements defined by any operating system or software application is the physical computer resources, also known as hardware. The minimal hardware requirements are as follows,

- System : Pentium Dual core.
- RAM : 2GB
- Processor : 2.4 GHz
- Input device : Keyboard, Mouse.
- Hard Disk : 120 GB and above.

5.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software requirements deals with defining resource requirements and prerequisites that needs to be installed on a computer to provide functioning of an application. The minimal software requirements are as follows,

- Coding language : Python.
- Tool : Python, Idle 3.9,anaconda navigator.
- IDE : anaconda.
- Operating System : Windows 10

CHAPTER 6

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6.1. SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

6.1.1 Python Language

Python is an object-oriented programming language created by Guido Rossum in 1989. It is ideally designed for rapid prototyping of complex applications. It has interfaces to many OS system calls and libraries and is extensible to C or C++. Many large companies use the Python programming language include NASA, Google, YouTube, BitTorrent, etc. Python programming is widely used in Artificial Intelligence, Natural Language Generation, Neural Networks and other advanced fields of Computer Science. Python had deep focus on code readability & this class will teach you python from basics.

Python Programming Characteristics

- It provides rich data types and easier to read syntax than any other programming languages
- It is a platform independent scripted language with full access to operating system API's
- Compared to other programming languages, it allows more run-time flexibility
- It includes the basic text manipulation facilities of Perl and Awk
- A module in Python may have one or more classes and free functions
- Libraries in Python's are cross-platform compatible with Linux, Macintosh, and Windows
- For building large applications, Python can be compiled to byte-code

- Python supports functional and structured programming as well as OOP
- It supports interactive mode that allows interacting Testing and debugging of snippets of code
- In Python, since there is no compilation step, editing, debugging and testing is fast.

Applications of Python Programming

Web Applications

You can create scalable Web Apps using frameworks and CMS (Content Management System) that are built on Python. Some of the popular platforms for creating Web Apps are: Django, Flask, Pyramid, Plone, Django CMS. Sites like Mozilla, Reddit, Instagram and PBS are written in Python.

Scientific and Numeric Computing

There are numerous libraries available in Python for scientific and numeric computing. There are libraries like: SciPy and NumPy that are used in general purpose computing. And, there are specific libraries like: EarthPy for earth science, AstroPy for Astronomy and so on. Also, the language is heavily used in machine learning, data mining and deep learning.

Creating software Prototypes

Python is slow compared to compiled languages like C++ and Java. It might not be a good choice if resources are limited and efficiency is a must. However, Python is a great language for creating prototypes. For example: You can use Pygame (library for creating games) to create your game's prototype first. If you like the prototype, you can use language like C++ to create the actual game.

Good Language to Teach Programming

Python is used by many companies to teach programming to kids and newbies. It is a good language with a lot of features and capabilities. Yet,

it's one of the easiest language to learn because of its simple easy-to-use syntax.

6.1.2. Opencv Package

Python is a general purpose programming language started by Guido van Rossum, which became very popular in short time mainly because of its simplicity and code readability. It enables the programmer to express his ideas in fewer lines of code without reducing any readability.

Compared to other languages like C/C++, Python is slower. But another important feature of Python is that it can be easily extended with C/C++. This feature helps us to write computationally intensive codes in C/C++ and create a Python wrapper for it so that we can use these wrappers as Python modules. This gives us two advantages: first, our code is as fast as original C/C++ code (since it is the actual C++ code working in background) and second, it is very easy to code in Python. This is how OpenCV-Python works, it is a Python wrapper around original C++ implementation.

And the support of Numpy makes the task more easier. Numpy is a highly optimized library for numerical operations. It gives a MATLAB-style syntax. All the OpenCV array structures are converted to-and-from Numpy arrays. So whatever operations you can do in Numpy, you can combine it with OpenCV, which increases number of weapons in your arsenal. Besides that, several other libraries like SciPy, Matplotlib which supports Numpy can be used with this.

So OpenCV-Python is an appropriate tool for fast prototyping of computer vision problems.

6.1.3 FEATURES OF ANACONDA NAVIGATOR

Anaconda is a free and open source, easy to install distribution of Python and R programming languages. Anaconda provides a working environment which is used for scientific computing, data science, statistical analysis and machine learning.

The latest distribution of Anaconda is Anaconda 5.3 and is released in October, 2018. It has the conda package, environment manager and a collection of 1000+ open source packages long with free community support.

What is Anaconda Navigator?

Anaconda Navigator is a desktop graphical user interface (GUI) included in the Anaconda distribution. It allows us to launch applications provided in the Anaconda distribution and easily manage conda packages, environments and

channels without the use of command-line commands. It is available for Windows, macOS and Linux.

Applications Provided In Anaconda Distribution

The Anaconda distribution comes with the following applications along with Anaconda Navigator.

1. JupyterLab
2. Jupyter Notebook
3. Qt Console
4. Spyder

5. Glueviz
6. Orange3
7. RStudio
8. Visual Studio Code
9. > JupyterLab: This is an extensible working environment for interactive and reproducible computing, based on the Jupyter Notebook and Architecture.
10. >Jupyter Notebook: This is a web-based, interactive computing notebook environment. We can edit and run human-readable docs while describing the data analysis.
11. > Qt Console: It is the PyQt GUI that supports inline figures, proper multiline editing with syntax highlighting, graphical calltips and more.
12. > Spyder: Spyder is a scientific Python Development Environment. It is a powerful Python IDE with advanced editing, interactive testing, debugging and introspection features.
13. > VS Code: It is a streamlined code editor with support for development operations like debugging, task running and version control.
14. > Glueviz: This is used for multidimensional data visualization across files. It explores relationships within and among related datasets.
15. >Orange 3: It is a component-based data mining framework. This can be used for data visualization and data analysis. The workflows in Orange 3 are very interactive and provide a large toolbox.

16. >Rstudio: It is a set of integrated tools designed to help you be more productive with R. It includes R essentials and notebooks.

17. New Features of Anaconda 5.3

Compiled with Latest Python release: Anaconda 5.3 is compiled with Python 3.7, taking advantage of Python's speed and feature improvements.

- **Better Reliability:** The reliability of Anaconda has been improved in the latest release by capturing and storing the package metadata for installed packages.
- **Enhanced CPU Performance:** The Intel Math Kernel Library 2019 for Deep Neural Networks(MKL 2019) has been introduced in Anaconda 5.3 distribution. Users deploying Tensorflow can make use of MKL 2019 for Deep Neural Networks. These Python binary packages are provided to achieve high CPU performance.
- **New packages are added:** There are over 230 packages which has been updated and added in the new release.
- **Work in Progress:** There is a casting bug in Numpy with Python 3.7 but the team is currently working on patching it until Numpy is updated.

6.2. LIST OF MODULES:

1. Preprocessing
2. Cascade classifier
3. Face Detection
4. GLCM features
5. Neural network

6.3. MODULE DESCRIPTION:

6.3.1. PREPROCESSING:

Image Pre-processing is a common name for operations with images at the lowest level of abstraction. Its input and output are intensity images. The aim of pre-processing is an improvement of the image data that suppresses unwanted distortions or enhances some image features important for further processing.

Image restoration is the operation of taking a corrupted/noisy image and estimating the clean original image. Corruption may come in many forms such as motion blur, noise, and camera misfocus. Image restoration is different from image enhancement in that the latter is designed to emphasize features of the image that make the image more pleasing to the observer, but not necessarily to produce realistic data from a scientific point of view

6.3.2. CASCADE CLASSIFIER:

Feature classifier achieves 100% face detection rate and about 50% false positive rate. A 5 feature classifier achieves 100% detection rate and 40% false positive rate (20% cumulative). A 20 feature classifier achieves 100% detection rate with 10% false positive rate (2% cumulative). Combining several weak classifiers improves the accuracy of detection.

6.3.4 FACE DETECTION:

The scale increase rate specifies how quickly the face detector function should increase the scale for face detection with each pass it makes over an image. Setting the scale increase rate high makes the detector run faster by running fewer passes. If it is set too high it may jump quickly between the scales and miss the faces

6.3.5 GLCM FEATURES:

The graycomatrix function creates a gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) by calculating how often a pixel with the intensity (gray-level) value i occurs in a specific spatial relationship to a pixel with the value j . By default, the spatial relationship is defined as the pixel of interest and the pixel to its immediate right (horizontally adjacent), but you can specify other spatial relationships between the two pixels

6.3.6 NEURAL NETWORK:

Neural networks are predictive models loosely based on the action of biological neurons. The selection of the name “neural network” was one of the great PR successes of the Twentieth Century. It certainly sounds more exciting than a technical description such as “A network of weighted, additive values with nonlinear transfer functions”.

CHAPTER 7

SYSTEM TESTING

7.1 GENERAL

In a generalized way, we can say that the system testing is a type of testing in which the main aim is to make sure that system performs efficiently and seamlessly. The process of testing is applied to a program with the main aim to discover an unprecedented error, an error which otherwise could have damaged the future of the software. Test cases which brings up a high possibility of discovering and error is considered successful. This successful test helps to answer the still unknown errors.

TEST CASE

Testing, as already explained earlier, is the process of discovering all possible weak-points in the finalized software product. Testing helps to counter the working of sub-assemblies, components, assembly and the complete result. The software is taken through different exercises with the main aim of making sure that software meets the business requirement and user-expectations and doesn't fails abruptly. Several types of tests are used today. Each test type addresses a specific testing requirement.

Testing Techniques

A test plan is a document which describes approach, its scope, its resources and the schedule of aimed testing exercises. It helps to identify almost other test item, the features which are to be tested, its tasks, how will everyone do each task, how much the tester is independent, the environment in which the test is taking place, its technique of design plus the both the end criteria which is used, also rational of choice of theirs, and whatever kind of risk which requires emergency planning. It can be also referred to as the record of the

process of test planning. Test plans are usually prepared with signification input from test engineers.

7.2 TYPES OF TESTING

7.2.1 UNIT TESTING

In unit testing, the design of the test cases is involved that helps in the validation of the internal program logic. The validation of all the decision branches and internal code takes place. After the individual unit is completed it takes place. Plus it is taken into account after the individual unit is completed before integration. The unit test thus performs the basic level test at its component stage and test the particular business process, system configurations etc. The unit test ensures that the particular unique path of the process gets performed precisely to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs with the results which are expected.

7.2.2 INTEGRATION TESTING

These tests are designed to test the integrated software items to determine whether if they really execute as a single program or application. The testing is event driven and thus is concerned with the basic outcome of field. The Integration tests demonstrate that the components were individually satisfaction, as already represented by successful unit testing, the components are apt and fine. This type of testing is specially aimed to expose the issues that come-up by the components combination.

7.2.3 FUNCTIONAL TESTING

The functional tests help in providing the systematic representation that functions tested are available and specified by technical requirement, documentation of the system and the user manual.

7.2.4 SYSTEM TESTING

System testing, as the name suggests, is the type of testing in which ensure that the software system meet the business requirements and aim. Testing of the configuration is taken place here to ensure predictable result and thus analysis of it. System testing is relied on the description of process and its flow, stressing on pre driven process and the points of integration.

7.2.5 WHITE BOX TESTING

The white box testing is the type of testing in which the internal components of the system software is open and can be processed by the tester. It is therefore a complex type of testing process. All the data structure, components etc. are tested by the tester himself to find out a possible bug or error. It is used in situation in which the black box is incapable of finding out a bug. It is a complex type of testing which takes more time to get applied.

7.2.6 BLACK BOX TESTING

The black box testing is the type of testing in which the internal components of the software is hidden and only the input and output of the system is the key for the tester to find out a bug. It is therefore a simple type of testing. A programmer with basic knowledge can also process this type of testing. It is less time consuming as compared to the white box testing. It is very successful for software which are less complex are straight-forward in nature. It is also less costly than white box testing.

7.2.7 ACCEPTANCE TESTING

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

7.2.8 ALPHA TESTING

Alpha testing is performed at the developer's site by the customer in a closed environment. This is done after the system testing. Alpha testing is one of the most common software testing strategies used in software development. It's specially used by product development organizations. Alpha testing is typically performed by a group that is independent of the design team, but still within the company, e.g. in-house software test engineers, or software QA engineers. Alpha testing is final testing before the software is released to the general public.

7.2.9 BETA TESTING

It is also known as field testing. It takes place at customer's sites. It sends the system to users who install it and use it under real-world working conditions. A beta test is the second phase of software testing in which a sampling of the intended audience tries the product out.

7.2.10 SECURITY TESTING

Security testing is basically a type of software testing that's done to check whether the application or the product is secured or not. It checks to see if the application is vulnerable to attacks, if anyone hack the system or login to the application without any authorization. It is a type of non functional testing. It is a process to determine that an information system protects data and maintains functionality as intended. The security testing is performed to check whether there is any information leakage in the sense by encrypting the application or using wide range of software's and hardware's and firewall etc.

7.2.11. TEST RESULT

S.NO	FUNCTION	DESCRIPTION	EXPECTED OUTPUT	ACTUAL OUTPUT	STATUS
1.	Encryption	Plain point converted into cipher text	64-bit key using encryption in data	128-bit using encryption in data	Success
2.	Key features	Key function act as a symmetric key features	The key symmetric key of using in data	The symmetric key of using in data	Success
3.	Decryption	Cipher text converted into plain text	The common server data only retrieved	The different server splitting process into data retrieved	Success
4.	Data splitting	Data processing into file splitting	Not splitting to data in server	The four server splitting into data	Success

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Face Recognition is mainly used to protect the transaction from hackers. Here we use access control and double encryption techniques to overcome the intrusion of third party users and also protect the most important information data thus providing security to whole data.

In future some hackers can attack the database that should be defended by some techniques; Access control and Encryption has some default in future to overcome the defects of attributes errors. As the encryption and Access control may not be enough in future to protect the security in ATM machine.

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

CONCLUSION:

In this project, a new exchange application is sued to overcome the disadvantages of the existing system by implementing face recognition mechanism and access control, instead of using ATM card to withdraw money . For that we select important attributes of machine learning techniques to protect the data throughout the process. By this project we can get an idea of regulating the face recognition mechanism for protecting the information of user. In this paper we explore recent form works in face recognition in relation to machine learning. We highlight how data are protected and stored .Thus to avoid TAM robberies and to provide security for ATM .To secure such a complex system will be even more difficult than design it. And now people just begin to discuss some issues of ATM security . It will provide some experience for us to implement security services in ATM network.

FUTURE ENHANCEMENT:

In future some hackers can attack the database that should be defended by some techniques; Access control and Encryption has some default in future to overcome the defects of attributes errors. As the encryption and Access control may not be enough in future to protect the security in ATM machine. And we can use it for two communication through bank details. Here our application will store more data.

APPENDICES

A.SAMPLE CODE

CREATE DATA

```
Import cv2,sys,numpy,os
Import urllib.request
Import numpy as np
Haar-file='haarcascade_frontalface.xml'
Datasets=""datasets""
Sub_data=""Raji""
Path=os.path.join(datasets,sub_data)
If not os.path.isdir(path):
Os.mkdir(path)
(width,height)=(130,100)
Face_cascade=cv2.videocapture(0)
Count=1
While count <101:
(_,im)=webcam.read()
Gray=cv2.cvtColor(im,cv2.COLOR_BGR2GRAY)
Faces=face_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray,1.3,4)
For (x,y,w,h) in faces:
Cv2.rectangle(im,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(255,0,0),2)
Face=gray(y:y+h, x:x +w)
Face_resize=cv2.resize(face,(width,height))
Cv2.imwrite(""+s.png""%(path,count),face_resize)
```

```
Count+=1
Cv2.imshow("OpenCV",im)
Key=cv2.waitKey(10)
If key==27:
Break
```

SENDING MAIL:

```
import cv2,sys,numpy,os
import urllib
import numpy as np
import time
import os
from subprocess import call
import time
import os
import glob
import smtplib
import base64
from email.mime.image import MIMEImage
from email.mime.multipart import MIMEMultipart
from email.mime.text import MIMEText
import sys
gmail_user=iotdemopan@gmail.com
gmail_pwd="panioddemo987@"
FROM='iotdemopan@gmail.com'
TO=['rajiveerappan99@gmail.com']
def mail():
```

```
msg=MIMEMultipart()
time.sleep(1)
msg['subject']="security"
body="THIS IS FROM XXX BANK REGARDING SECURITY BREACH"
msg.attach(MIMEText(body,'plain'))
time.sleep(1)
fp=open("1.png","r")
time.sleep(i)
img=MIMEImage(fp.read())
time.sleep(I)
fp.close()
time.sleep(i)
time.sleep(i)
msg.attach(img)
time.sleep(i)
try:
server=smtplib.SMTP("smtp.gmail.com",587)
print("smtp.gmail")
server.echo()
print("ehlo")
server.starttls()
print("starttls")
server.login(gmail_user,gmail_pwd)
print("reading mail and password")
server.sendmail(FROM,TO,msg.as_string())
print("from")
server.close()
```

```

print("successfully sent the mail")
except:
print("failed to send the mail")
size=4
haar_file="haarcascade_frontalface-default.xml")
datasets="datasets"
print("Training...")
(images,lables, names,id)=([],[],[],0)
For {subdir,dirs.,files)in os.walk(datasets):
For subdir in dirs.:
Names[id]=subdir
Subjectpath=os.path.join(datasets,subdir)
For filename in os.path.join(datasets,subdir)
For filename in os.listdir(subjrcpath):
Path=subjectpath +"/" +filename
Label=id
Images.append(cv2.imread(path,0))
Lables.append(int(label))
id+=1
(width,height)=(130,100)
(images,lables)=(numpy.array(lis) for lis in (images,lables))
Model=cv2.face.fisherfacerecognition_create()
Model.train(images,lables)
Face_cascade=cv2.cascadeclassifier(haar_file)
Webcam=cv2.videocapture(0)
(_,im)=webcam.read()
Gray=cv2.cvtColor(im,cv2.COLOR_BGR2GREAY)

```

```

Faces=face_cascade.detectMultiScale(gray(1,4,5)
for (x,y,w,h) in faces:
    Gray=cv2.cvtColor(im,(x,y),(x+w,y+h),(255,255,0),2))
    Face=gray[y:y+h,x:x+w]
    Face_resize=cv2.resize(face,(width,height))
    Prediction=model.predict(face+recognition)
    Cv2.rectangle(im,(x,y),x+w,y+h),(0,255,0),3)
    If prediction [0]<1000:
        Print(names[prediction[0]])
        Cv2.putText(im,names[prediction[0]])
        If names[prediction[0]]:
            Else:
                Print("unknown Person")
                Cv2.imwrite("1.png",im)
                Mail()
                A=input("enter the pin")
                If a=="1234":
                    Print("authenticated")
                Else:
                    Cv2.putText(x+10,y+10,cv2.FONT_HERSHEY_SIMPLEX)
                Cv2.close()

```

B. SCREENSHOTS


```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd.exe
(ADAS LANE VEHICLE) C:\Users\karu>python extract_embeddings.py --dataset dataset --embeddings output/embeddings.pickle --detector face_detection_model --embedding-model
openface_n4_small2.v1.t7
python: can't open file 'extract_embeddings.py': [Errno 2] No such file or directory

(ADAS LANE VEHICLE) C:\Users\karu>cd E:\projects\FaceRecDL12

(ADAS LANE VEHICLE) C:\Users\karu>python extract_embeddings.py --dataset dataset --embeddings output/embeddings.pickle --detector face_detection_model --embedding-model
openface_n4_small2.v1.t7
python: can't open file 'extract_embeddings.py': [Errno 2] No such file or directory

(ADAS LANE VEHICLE) C:\Users\karu>cd E:\projects\FaceRecDL12

(ADAS LANE VEHICLE) E:\projects\FaceRecDL12>python extract_embeddings.py --dataset dataset --embeddings output/embeddings.pickle --detector face_detection_model --embed
ding-model openface_n4_small2.v1.t7
[INFO] loading face detector...
[INFO] loading face recognizer...
[INFO] quantifying faces...
[INFO] processing image 1/266
[INFO] processing image 2/266
[INFO] processing image 3/266
[INFO] processing image 4/266
[INFO] processing image 5/266
[INFO] processing image 6/266
[INFO] processing image 7/266
[INFO] processing image 8/266
[INFO] processing image 9/266
[INFO] processing image 10/266
[INFO] processing image 11/266
[INFO] processing image 12/266
[INFO] processing image 13/266
[INFO] processing image 14/266
[INFO] processing image 15/266
[INFO] processing image 16/266
[INFO] processing image 17/266
[INFO] processing image 18/266
[INFO] processing image 19/266
[INFO] processing image 20/266
[INFO] processing image 21/266
[INFO] processing image 22/266
[INFO] processing image 23/266
[INFO] processing image 24/266
[INFO] processing image 25/266
[INFO] processing image 26/266

Activate Windows
Go to Settings to activate Windows.
```

It represents the storage of data in the database


```
C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd.exe
[INFO] processing image 238/266
[INFO] processing image 239/266
[INFO] processing image 240/266
[INFO] processing image 241/266
[INFO] processing image 242/266
[INFO] processing image 243/266
[INFO] processing image 244/266
[INFO] processing image 245/266
[INFO] processing image 246/266
[INFO] processing image 247/266
[INFO] processing image 248/266
[INFO] processing image 249/266
[INFO] processing image 250/266
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[INFO] processing image 257/266
[INFO] processing image 258/266
[INFO] processing image 259/266
[INFO] processing image 260/266
[INFO] processing image 261/266
[INFO] processing image 262/266
[INFO] processing image 263/266
[INFO] processing image 264/266
[INFO] processing image 265/266
[INFO] processing image 266/266
[INFO] serializing 266 encodings...

(ADAS LANE VEHICLE) E:\projects\FaceRecDL12>
```

It represents that any number of data can be stored

It captures the image of the valid user and continue withdrawal

It send the image of third user and sent the notification

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